

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B424

Date: 21 Jan 2009

Take Off: 15:00:10

Landing: 20:30:02

Flight Time: 5h 29m 52s

Campaign: APPRAISE-ICE Flight

Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Zhiqiang Ciu	Leeds University	
6	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Core Chemistry	Mo Smith	FAAM	
8	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
9	Manchester Cloud	J. Crozier	Manchester University	
10	CVI / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	
11	WAS	Jimmy Hopkins	York University	
12	WAS Training	Shalini Punjabi	York University	
13	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump / filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
WAS	WAS operator does not create a log sheet
Manchester Cloud	Manchester Cloud operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	29 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

None so far.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B424

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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145404		ASP	0.68 kft	050	open
150010		T/O	2.5 kft	252	
150551		Video	6.8 kft	049	started
151552		note	10.0 kft	242	water measures zeroed
152107		PSAP	10.0 kft	235	Off
152151	152626	Profile 1	10.0 - 5.6 kft	169	
152949		QNH	5.5 kft	171	1001
153112	153504	Profile 2	5.6 - 2.7 kft	153	
153505	155119	Run 1	2.7 kft	213	
153543		note	2.6 kft	236	chilbolton
153812		psap	2.7 kft	250	off
153950		psap	2.7 kft	247	on
154259		psap	2.7 kft	248	off
154528		psap	2.7 kft	248	on
154701		psap	2.7 kft	248	off
155208		note	2.7 kft	151	waters zeroed
155249	160558	Run 2	2.7 kft	065	
160447		psap	2.7 kft	081	on
160553		note	2.7 kft	077	chilbolton
160653		note	2.7 kft	350	water zeroed
161006	161557	Profile 3	2.6 - 8.0 kft	233	chilbolton
161053		psap	3.2 kft	247	off
161557	162331	Run 3	8.0 - 9.2 kft	252	162215
162332	162516	Profile 4	9.2 - 11.0 kft	252	162215
162945	164441	Run 4	11.0 kft	075	chilbolton
163842		note	11.0 kft	073	chilbolton
164441	164555	Profile 5	11.0 - 12.0 kft	244	chilbolton
164555	165754	Run 5	12.0 kft	258	
165754	165900	Profile 6	12.0 - 13.0 kft	255	
165901	171714	Run 6	13.0 kft	257	chilbolton
171120		note	13.0 kft	072	chilbolton
171714	171819	Profile 7	13.0 - 14.0 kft	245	chilbolton
171819	172953	Run 7	14.0 kft	259	
172953	173104	Profile 8	14.0 - 15.0 kft	259	
173104	174955	Run 8	15.0 kft	257	
174427		note	15.0 kft	063	chilbolton
174955	175559	Profile 9	15.0 - 22.0 kft	255	
175559	175824	Run 9	22.0 kft	263	
175608		note	22.0 kft	263	water zeroed
175824	180242	Profile 10	22.0 - 16.1 kft	263	interrupt
180426	180818	Profile 10	16.1 - 12.0 kft	053	restart
180818	182048	Run 10	12.0 - 12.1 kft	070	Chilbolton
181538		note	12.0 kft	073	Chilbolton
182048	182206	Profile 11	12.1 - 11.0 kft	249	Chilbolton
182207	183451	Run 11	11.0 kft	255	
183451	183626	Profile 12	11.0 - 10.0 kft	257	
183626	185602	Run 12	10.0 kft	255	
185035		note	10.0 kft	076	Chilbolton
185523		note	10.0 kft	242	Chilbolton
185603	185726	Profile 13	10.0 - 9.0 kft	253	
185726	190808	Run 13	9.0 kft	251	
185930		note	9.0 kft	252	Lights in DFC

190809	190934	Profile 14	9.0 - 8.0 kft	251		
190935	192633	Run 14	8.0 kft	250	Chilbolton	
192138		note	8.0 kft	079	Chilbolton	
192634	193015	Profile 15	8.0 - 6.0 kft	243	Chilbolton	
192915	194051	Run 15	6.0 kft	245		
194052	194253	Profile 16	6.0 - 4.0 kft	248		
194253	195759	Run 16	4.0 - 4.4 kft	242		
195652		note	4.0 kft	079	Chilbolton	
195759	195837	Profile 17	4.4 - 5.0 kft	357		
195837	201948	Run 17	5.0 kft	085		
200135		note	5.0 kft	238	Chilbolton	
203002		Land	0.66 kft	252	Exeter	
203232		ASP	0.67 kft	068	closed	
203520		Shutdown	0.67 kft	246	50'43.93N	3'24.81W

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 21 Jan 2009

B424 (t/o Cranfield, land away at Exeter) T/O 15:00z (~4.5hours)

B425 (t/o & Land Exeter) T/O 21:00 (~ 3.5 hours)

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail B424:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) T+35 When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions (This may only be achieved with an approach to Boscombe Down airfield - TBD). Fly 10min **clear air** leg.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above mid level cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

Sortie Detail B425: as above except for takeoff and transit from Exeter airfield

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)
- Filters

CVI inlet sampling: residuals (and $Ly\alpha$) incloud; aerosols out of cloud (PCASP, CPC)

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B424, 21st Jan 2009 (T/O Cranfield 15:00; Landing Exeter 20:13)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions & operating area: An area of low pressure was deepening in the N. Atlantic to the NW of the British Isles (SW of Iceland), generating a series frontal systems that were approaching the UK from the west. The first of these was a warm front the middle level cloud from which was predicted to arrive in the vicinity of the Chilbolton area by mid afternoon, with the bulk of the associated precipitation expected to arrive by 6pm. Take off time (15:00) was thus set to catch the arrival of the mid level cloud whilst still allowing for the possibility of measuring some aerosol at lower levels in cloud free conditions before the arrival of the lower level cloud and heavy precipitation. To facilitate this take off time and a full length mission the aircraft needed to land at an airfield that would be open after 19:00. Exeter was chosen. Another option considered was to land early (after 4-4.5 hrs) refuel and take off again for a shorter second mission to sample the frontal system over an extended period. During the flight it was decided to carry out a single full length flight and then prepare for a second mission the next day in other frontal systems coming in from the west.

Summary of the flight: During the transit out to the Chilbolton area (FL100, 696mbar, -14.3 to -12.0°C) in clear air, the bank of mid and upper level frontal cloud could be seen out to the west in the distance. It was decided that in the absence of low level cloud (and in the interest of time) a missed approach to Boscombe Down airfield was not required in order to carry out aerosol measurements at low level. Instead a profile down to 2.6kft (the minimum safe operation altitude (msa) over the Chilbolton radial terrain) was carried out and an SLR R1 (918mbar, 1.1°C) started on the 255 radial outbound from Chilbolton (CH). Filters were started at 5.5kft during descent P2 and continued during R1. Half way along the run a patch of low cloud and precipitation (rain) was encountered so filters were switched off. The plane flew into more pockets of rain along the run before entering solid low cloud (3 minutes) before the turn at the SW end of the radial. A reciprocal run (R2) was carried out, inbound at the same altitude to maximise the measurement of aerosol possibly feeding into the cloud system. In clear air sections, PCASP saw 20 cm^{-3} , the wCPC saw 2500 counts and CAS $15\text{-}20 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. AMS measured low loadings, $\sim 0.2 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ sulphate and organic and half that loading of nitrate. The SMPS saw modes at around 300-350 nm and again at 50nm. Both the 2DC and CIP100 (PIP) saw drops during periods of rain. On the inbound leg R2, Chilbolton advised they were seeing thick ice cloud overhead between 1.5 and 7km (5-23kft), with an enhanced region of differential reflectivity at 1.1km (3.6kft).

After passing overhead Chilbolton (CH) inbound and in the turn at Pepis, a profile ascent P3 was started overhead CH outbound. At 3.6kft (825mbar, -0.82°C) a diffuse cloud base (CB) was encountered. 2DC saw $>100 \text{ litre}^{-1}$ of cloud particles, while the FSSP concentration was “not high”. 2DS was seeing capped columns. P3 was terminated at FL80 (752mbar, -8.2°C) and R3 started (40% along radial leg). This was the start of series of profile ascents/descents and SLR legs through the frontal cloud system along the 255 radial from Chilbolton. Outbound SLRs were generally terminated prior to arriving at the SW end of the run, and profiles to the next level completed before making the turn. The altitude of inbound SLRs was maintained after passing over CH and in the turn at Pepis, until passing over CH again. A profile change in altitude was then undertaken at or just after passing the CH overhead, outbound. The tables below summarise these changes and comment on the main observations during each run.

SLRs R3, R4, R5, R6, R7 and R8 were carried out at ascending levels through the cloud (following profile ascents P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, and P8) (Table 2). A profile ascent P9 was then carried out (outbound from Chilbolton) up through the remaining cloud to above cloud top to FL220. The main CT was observed at $\sim 21 \text{ kft}$ (445mbar, -29.1°C) half way along the leg, although the aircraft popped out through a lower CT at 16.6kft (534mbar, -20.0°C) closer to Chilbolton. R9 was carried out at FL220 for 3 minutes in clear air (still going outbound). There was cirrus cloud above but no obvious precipitation particles were detected by any cloud probe. After various instruments had had their calibrations checked, a profile descent P10 was carried out for the remainder of the outbound leg, interrupted at FL160 (547mbar, -18.2°C) for the turn at the SW end of the radial, and then continued down to FL120 (643mbar, -11.1°C). This level was chosen based on information from Chilbolton (MSci2) of there being high Zdr at 3.5-4km (12-13kft) hence P10 would profile through into this layer. R10 was carried out inbound to Chilbolton at this level of interest.

Table 2 – ascending SLRs

P # u/d Run #	in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Run Pressure (mbar)	Temp start/end SLR(°C)	Comments/observations
P3 u R3	O	FL80	752	-8.2 -7.1	Ice ppt – “big splodges”, 2DC 60 L ⁻¹ small ice aggregates CIP 100 L ⁻¹ mode 200µm varied habit CAS <5 cm ⁻³
P4 u R4	I	FL110	670	-11.7 -12.8	CVI tip iced up, AMS on Rose (MSmode) 2DS larger messier aggregates, 2DC 50 L ⁻¹ aggregates, CAS ~5 cm ⁻³ mode 20µm, PIP mode ~1mm intermittent bimodal 1mm/100µm, some icing on turbulence probe – lost TAC. MSci sees visible structure in cloud during CH turn.
P5 u R5	O	FL120	644	-14.3 -12.2	PIP bimodal dist'n 1mm/100µm 2DS mainly agg, occasional pristine crystal CIP mode 200-300µm + few mm columns CAS 20µm mode, FSSP same (~5cm ⁻³) 2DS more ppt towards end R5
P6 u R6	I	FL130	619	-13.0 -15.7	Core cloud seeing pristine snow, 2DS/CIP too. Snow and turbulence inbound in turn at CH, then out of cloud after turn
P7u R7	O	FL140	595	-16.6 -14.8	2DC 20 L ⁻¹ aggregates (800µm) PIP peak ~15 L ⁻¹ CIP ppt 200 L ⁻¹ (300µm) CAS 20µm mode 5 cm ⁻³ 2DS sees small stuff CIP in smallest channel too ...then big ppt too. Radar – CT falling to 5km/16.4kft shear layer 3km/9.8kft
P8 u R8	I	FL150	571	-16.3 -16.6	P8 2DS pristine snow; R8 CVI unblocked 2DS/CIP – pockets liquid H2O along R8 PIP bimodal at times 100µm/1mm. MSci2 – high Zdr 12-13kft lost pitot static p (static p OK on CAPS) CVI blocked end R8.
P9 u R9	O	FL220	428	-30.9 -30.8	P9 Out of CT 16.6 kft(534mbar, -20.0°C) back into cloud at 19.5kft (2mins) Main CT 21kft(445mbar, -29.1°C) R9 Cloud Free – no ppt from Ci above

A series of SLRs R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, R15 and R16 were then undertaken at successively lower levels through the cloud (Table 3), down to the lowest level of FL40 (R16 inbound at 874mbar, from +0.7°C SW end to -0.5°C CH end). This was followed by a climb (P17) back up to FL50 for the final outbound leg and recovery into Exeter airport. Earlier (~18.02z - during P10), Chilbolton suggested the melting level was at 2.2km (or 7.2kft), so this set of SLRS and profiles was designed to pass through this level of interest, although temperatures measured on the aircraft suggested the melting level was much lower than this at around FL40 when the aircraft got to this temperature range. The aircraft recovered to Exeter and landed (in a 45kt crosswind!) at 20:13z.

Table 3 – descending SLRs

P # u/d Run #	in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Run Pressure (mbar)	Temp start/end SLR(°C)	Comments/observations
P10 d R10	I	FL120	643	-10.6 -12.6	During P10 (12.9kft) 2DS/CIP saw snowflakes. Turbulence probe well iced up. R10 Aircraft anti-ice detected liquid
P11 d R11	O	FL110	668	-11.2 -8.4	2DC <10 L ⁻¹ ; PIP ~10 L ⁻¹ snowflakes 2DS snowflakes CAS 20µm particles (2cm ⁻³) CIP 50 L ⁻¹ ppt (always show large # in smallest bin too?) FSSP 20µm mode <10cm ⁻³ (~1cm ⁻³) [Chilbolton: enhanced Zdr signal at 2km (6.5kft) – melting layer 25 km west !!] <u>6minutes later...</u> Aircraft anti-ice detected liquid, all m/phys probes see drops: 2DS/CIP see drops ~120µm well distrib'd PIP bottom channel too FSSP; drops 50cm ⁻³ 10µm – shrinking to 2µm (5-10cm ⁻³) CIP (120µm to lowest channels) bimodal – large mode shrinking CDP only low concs (<1cm ⁻³) Shattering??
P12 d R12	I	FL100	695	-6.0 -10.0 -9.3	All turbulence signals lost now – fully iced Strong ppt now 2DS/CIP 120µm doughnuts 2DC doughnuts 300 L ⁻¹ (was 1000 L ⁻¹) then only snowflakes Q (from radar) any evidence of falling crystals? Yes (2DS/CIP)
P13 d R13	O	FL90	723	-8.3 -7.3	P13 Aircraft anti-ice detected liquid [Chilbolton: patches high Zdr 1.7/2.2km 5.5/7.2kft 40km west]
P14 d R14	I	FL80	751	-5.8 -4.6 -5.7	2DC – liquid drops, needles, columns PIP – needles, columns (800µm) CIP – needles (500µm) Then ... 2DS – capped columns – more ice than before – rimed frozen drops? Chilbolton fall streaks 40km west 4-6kft Over CH 2DS – good mix small drops – larger ice (inc some columns)
P15 d R15	O	FL60	810	-3.1 -1.3	2DC/PIP : water drops – range of sizes (250 L ⁻¹ / 40 L ⁻¹) 2DS drops sticking together 100-300µm FSSP 2cm-3 mode 15-20µm (1 st channel) CDP – concs not high enough can't see, Q - droplet shattering?? Lost Nevzorov again
P16 d R16	I	FL40	873	+0.65 -0.52	2DS/CIP occ large blobby thing melting ice? Turbulence here – many pockets Lots ice again over Chilbolton
P17 u R17	O	FL50	843	-1.6 -0.93	Q did the turbulence probe defrost?

Rainfall radar images showing frontal rainbands before (12:30) and during (19:15) flight B424

IR satellite images showing progression of cloud associated with warm front sampled during B424

Notes on instrumentation: (For full list of instrumentation functionality see flight log)

CPI - not present for this flight

Nevzorov total water probe – failed during flight again

CVI – tip iced up for much of flight

Turbulence probe - also iced up to increasing degrees during flight

Final comments: For further information about flight refer to Mission Scientist log sheets and screen dump file.

Mission Scientist's Log

[APPRMISE-CLOUDS]

Flight No B.424 Date 21/01/09 Name K.N. Bower Page 1 of 10.

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.50.00 - 14.52.30				(KNS turn)	Engine Starts N°4 - N°1
14.54.11	(KNS)				Taxi QNH 1000mb (310ft)
15.00.23	"				Rolling
15.00.50	"				T/O
					Med level cloud above + West
		4500			QNH (set p to 1013mb)
15.07.59	Trans	FL100	291	52°10'/0°24'	[696mb -14.15°/-30.58°C 17m/s/231°]
15.14.56	Trans	FL100	242	52°06'/1°6'	[696mb -14.34°/-28.77°C 14m/s/236°]
15.20.00	Trans	FL100			Into the medium level cloud
15.21.17	Trans turn	FL100	221	51°54'/1°42'	[696mb -11.92°/-13.15° 11m/s/256°]
15.21.49	P1 start	FL100	171	51°54'/1°42'	[696mb, -12.09°/-12.71, 10m/s/256°]
15.24.35	P1	7.4NH	172	51°42'/1°30'	[769mb, -8.12°/-10.53°C 14m/s/236°]
15.26.26	P1 end	5.5NH			
15.28	Trans	5.5NH			Filter on for water run
					Barometric QNH 995mb 1001mb (use 1000)
15.30.38	Trans Turn	5.5NH	171	51°15'/1°30'	[826mb, -4.71°/-9.45°C 12m/s/220°]
15.31.11	P2 start	5.5NH	153	51°16'/1°30'	↓ 2.3NH on 1000 1001mb
	P				RADSEMAN
15.35.03	P2 end/P1	2.6NH	23		2300ft [1.09°C/-1.04°C 919mb 14m/s/205°]
15.35.43	P1	2.6NH	247	51°6'/1°24'	Overtaken Chillybotta [1.35°/-0.28°C 15/208° 910m/s]
					PEASO with - 20 now 10 below
					OPC - 2500 cumulus from 5000ft
					CAS 15-20 cm ²
15.40.15	P1	2.6NH			Cloud - Filter closed

CM

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 424 Date 21/01/09 Name K.N. Bower Page 2 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					some rain on boat
15:40:36	R1	2.6kft	250		sn [919mb 1.33°/0.42°C 16m/s/20kts]
					Nabu Jaws (ZDC)
15:42:56	R1	2.6kft	248	51°0'/2°0'	Cloud + ppt - Filters off [1.18°/1.46°C 17/200°]
15:43:45	R1				Rain on windscreen
15:47:00	R1	2.6kft	248	50°54'/2°24'	Ppt again [1.58°/1.12°C 919mb 15m/s/20kts]
					PCASP - 20 ZDC + P101
15:50:16	R1	2.6kft	248	50°54'/2°42'	(RADSEMICOM - Gamma) unbalanced
15:51:17	R1 and	2.6kft	247	5°48'/2°42'	[919mb 1.91/1.69°C 10m/s/20kts]
15:52:45	R2 st	2.6kft	68	50°48'/2°42'	[918mb 1.54/2.11°C 15m/s/20kts]
					AMS - small tracks 0.2 SO ₂ /0.03/0.1 NO ₂
					SMPS - total N ⁺ 350-300 + 50nm mode
15:55:13	R2	2.6kft	79	50°54'/2°30'	919mb, 1.82/2.15°C 14m/s/19kts (Free of CB but ppt)
16:57:40	R2	2.6kft			PIP - 0.001 cm ² ppt
					CB 1km
					RADSEMICOM had to be decontaminated 1500m-7000m
					above 3500m-3200m
					1100° enhance region dell cell
					Summer call.
16:05:54	R2 and	2.6kft	77	51°6'/1°24'	at Chilkatten [919mb 1.32/-0.23°C 13m/s/20kts]
16:10:04	P3 st	2.6kft	234	51°6'/1°24'	2200ft off Chilkatten (cloud over) [1.44/-0.48°C]
16:11:26	P3	3.6kft	257	51°6'/1°30'	dilute CB [-0.82/-0.97°C 885mb 17/205°]
					ZDC - > 100%
					PSS - not h

ZDS: Copied Columns now.

2-11 000 ft - PL 50

Mission Scientist's Log

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
16.15.55	R3cont/ R3	FL80	252	51°0'/1°54'	[-8.2°C/-8.8°C 752mb 14m/s/229°] low concn on CAS <5µm ³ Ice ppt - big "splodges" 2DC - small ice - blobby agglomeris 60/litre OPT: CAS 5µm ³ CIP 100µm ³ 200µm made - varied habit
16.22.15	R3cont/ R4	FL80	251	50°54'/2°24'	[-7.06°/-7.33°C 752mb, 21 m/s/233°] CWI tip - fully iced up now PCAS also - rain
16.25.13	R4cont/ R4	FL100	251	50°48'/2°42'	[-11.67°/-12.08° 670mb 10m/s/243°] AMS - still on Rose on MS only: 1 2DS CAS smaller concn to before. ↳ larger - more Xtals - aggy ice..... 2DC - ~ 50 l ⁻¹ aggregates too PIP - made bit less 1mm CAS made at 20µm Xchnt:- (11500A) Drops broad 3.4-3.7 km - SC drops growing Xtals PIP - seen intermittent bimodal (1mm/100µm)
16.36.41	R4	FL110	73	51°6'/1°24'	O.veched Chulbullen [669mb -12.81/-12.32 10m/s/260°] lost TAE dilt - leaning on stab probe MSii - I can see structure in cloud ahead CAS - made - 20µm CIP - too

CH

15:00 - 20:15 ish

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Name K. N. BOWER

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
16.44.40	R4end/R5	FL110	244	51°6'/1°24'	[12.85 / -12.28 669mb 18 m/s / 251°] over CH
16.45.53	R5end/R5	FL120	258	51°6'/1°30'	[14.28 / -14.15 °C 644mb 13 m/s / 263°]
					Above CT now
					Ci - Ci
					Core Cloud - Binned dist'n 1mm / 100µm PIP
					CIP - mode 200-300µm (for cd mm size range)
					ONS 20µm mode
					ZDS - occasn pristin - mainly aggregates
					FSSP - mode at 20µm (of order 5 cm ⁻³)
16.57.29	R5		254		CPI - more ppt now
16.57.53	R5end/R6	FL120	254	50°54'/2°30'	[12.19 / -11.72 644mb 24 m/s / 255°]
16.58.59	R6end/R6	FL130	257	50°48'/2°42'	[12.99 / -12.25 °C 619mb 21 m/s / 276°]
					and turning next.
					Core Cloud - pristin Snow - CPI too
17.00.35	R6	FL130	60	50°48'/2°42'	end of turn - [12.45 / -12.1 °C 618mb 21 m/s / 305°]
17.05.16	R6	FL130			Core Cloud - end ppt now (snow, turbulence in turn)
CH 17.11.20	R6	FL130	72	51°6'/1°24'	CH Chilled bottom [619mb -15.71 / -15.44 14 m/s / 290°]
					Out of cloud here
CH 17.17.12	R6end/R7	FL130	245	51°6'/1°24'	[15.65 / -15.15 619mb 21 m/s / 257°] (13.0 kft) CH Chilled
17.18.17	R7end/R7	FL140	259	51°6'/1°30'	[16.55 / -16.47 595mb 23 m/s / 259°] (13.9 kft)
17.20.15					ppt back (CPI)
					core cloud conc: 20 l ⁻¹ ZDC eggs (800µm)
					PIP: peak 0.015 cm ⁻³
					CPI - was 200 l ⁻¹ ppt ~ 300µm CH
					ONS 20µm mode 5 cm ⁻³

17.22.20.

{ ZDS - seem small stuff } 6 pixels ??
 { CPI too } ← smallest channel
 { big ppt back

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 Flight No B...424

 Date ...21/01/09

 Name K.N. BOWEN

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
17.23.13					Clear Skat - Forward Upper Right
17.22.54	R7	FL140	258	51°0'/1°54'	[-15.67°C / -15.0°C, 595mb, 24m/s / 270° (13.9 kkt)]
17.26.00					<u>Probe</u> - CT - descending 5km → (16.5 kkt) (Xdat) shear layer 3km → (10,000ft)
17.29.52	R7 end / R8 start	FL140	259	50°54'/2°36'	[-14.8° / -13.31°C, 595mb / 16kkt, 25m/s / 278°] OPT meson - pristine snowflakes fall
17.31.03	R8 end / R8	FL150	257	50°54'/2°42'	[-16.32° / -14.75°C, 571mb / 15kkt 23m/s / 277°] CWI - unblocked - (Pump on - CPI rack)
17.32.24	R8	FL150	196	50°48'/2°48'	[-16.8° / -13.99°C 57kmb / 14.9kkt 7m/s / 285°] Tom - identifying SC H ₂ O - important
17.36.45	R8	FL150	69°	50°54'/2°18'	CPI - supercooled water now - pockets along rim. [-16.63° / -14.78°C, 571mb]
17.42.25					PIP PIP - bimodal: 100µm / 1mm at times
17.42.31	R8	FL150	68°	51°6'/1°36'	PIP bimodal - timer [-16.32° / -16.28° 571 (83/25)]
					MSc2. high Zdr - spectral width 51 ^{wrong} @ 3.5 - 4km (1200ft) also - weak signature 3.5 km - Flight Man - just lost phot static p (still have static p on CRIS)
17.44.19	R8	FL150	68°	51°6'/1°24'	Overhead Chulbalka [-16.94° / -16.99, 571, 83m/s] -16.94°C / 16.99
					CWI - blocked again
17.49.53	R8 end / R9	FL150	255		- Over CH again [-16.62° / -16.52 571mb, X]
17.51.31	P9	16.6kkt	262	51°6'/1°30'	Out of IT now 534mb (-19.97° / -18.45°C) 56/69° - still wavy.

[CH]

[CH]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 424 Date 21/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
17.53.44	PA	19.5km	262°	51°0'/1°48'	Back in downflow [473mb -27.14/-25.79, ^{bad} wind]
17.55.01	PA	21.0km	263°	51°0'/1°54'	Through Main CT [-29.11/-28.19°C, 465mb]
17.55.06	entry/Ra	FL220	263	51°0'/2°0'	[-30.96/-35.37°, 428mb/21.9kts ^{65/64°}]
					CT - generally ~21000ft
					Ci above - no rpt from it on any probes
					(leveling for zero/cals d instruments)
17.58.23	R1 and P10	FL220	263	50°54'/2°18'	[-30.52/-42.4°, 427/22kts ^{57/62°}] (iced) *
18.00.11	P10	FL200	261	50°54'/2°30'	[CT] [-26.8°/-32.12 465mb 28m/s/57°] (iced) *
18.02.40	P10 int	FL160	259	50°48'/2°42'	[Ready to turn -16.16/-16.85°C 547mb]
					Chulbathen 2.2km Melting level
					TWC - v important to look at...
18.04.25	P10 rec	FL161	53	50°48'/2°42'	[-16.83/-16.33, 547mb, 71m/s/264°] (iced) *
18.08.17	P10 and P10	FL120	70	50°54'/2°18'	-10.56/-9.2°C 643mb - Wind no good reading *
18.07.15	P10	FL129	70	50°54'/2°24'	-12.12/-10.71°C 620mb - "Snowflakes" CT
18.11.15	P10	FL120	71	51°0'/1°54'	Arcell ice detection [-11.13°C/-10.72° 643mb]
18.15.28	P10	FL120	73	51°6'/1°24'	Over Chulbathen [-12.69/-12.41 643mb]
18.20.46	R10 and P11	FL120	249	51°6'/1°24'	Over Chulbathen -12.64/-12.33 643mb
18.22.04	P11 and P11	FL110	255	51°6'/1°30'	[-11.23/-10.16° 608mb 38m/s/81°C]
	P11	FL100			Core Anal: Snowflake 2DC < 10µm
					PIP 0.001 cm ³
					2DS :- Snowflakes
					CAS: 20µm particles (2cm ³)
					CIP: 50µm/litre ppt.
					PSSP 20µm multi < 10cm ³ = 1cm ³

11.30 7/0 Part C

-23-

CIP always shows considerable N° in smallest bin

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Flight No B. 424 Date 21/01/09 Name K.N. Sower Page 7 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Chillybatten - conditions
					- enhanced 2km → Melting layer (spectral width related to turbulence)
					2dr enhanced 25km west Chillybatten.
					(2km level) ≈ 6500ft
					Icing - Raindrops - CPI
					↳ (a/c antiicing detection)
					Well distributed drops - 120µm (CPI)
					PIP - bottom cloud peak
18.29.42	R11	FL110	ZSS	50°54'/2°12'	[-6.82°C / -7.26°C, 667mb - Wndiced]
					Well defined peak PSSP 10µm (50cm ³)
					(CPI) bimodal CIP ^{liquid drops.} ↳ (coll m/phys. change)
					graded shield of larger mode
					120µm → lowest cascade
					PSSP mode shrinks - 3µm - 5-10cm ³
					COP - not real amount low conc < 1cm ³
18.34.53	R11end / P12start	FL110	ZSF	50°54'/2°36'	[-6.36°C / -6.45°C, 669mb - Turbiced]
18.36.25	P12m / P12st	FL100	ZSS	50°48'/2°42'	[-6.02°C / -4.76°C 695mb - Turbiced]
					AM turb looks new.
18.40.20	R12. SLR	FL100	SZ	50°54'/2°36'	TAS - R12SM - not turb probe is TAS is OK.
					ppt - strong most at 120µm ZDS } droghinks CIP }
					2DC - droghinks - was 1000 l ⁻¹ now 300 l ⁻¹

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Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1849.12	R12	FL100	76	51°6'/1°30'	ZDC - snowflakes - not doing hands. now.
[CN] 18.50.37	R12	FL100	76	51°6'/1°24'	Over Chulbitten [-9.96/-8.17°C; 695mb] 2.7-3.5km - Chulbitten - is there endure of large falling ice Xbats? CPI - Yes. ✓
[CN] 18.55.21	R12	FL100	242	51°6'/1°24'	Over Chulbitten [-9.68/-8.21°C 695mb]
18.56.03	R12end/p13	FL100	252	51°6'/1°24'	Ice detected (king Mt) [-9.29/-8.55°, 696mb]
18.57.25	R13end/R15	FL90	251	51°6'/1°36'	[-8.25/-7.21°C 723mb turb ice detur] Chil - patch high 2dr 1.7-2.2 km (6.5) (6) 40km West of CH. Chil - CT.....
19.08.07	R13end/p14	FL90	251	50°54'/2°24'	[-7.28/-4.22°C 723mb 24mb/224°] R80
19.09.33	R14end/R14	FL80	251	50°54'/2°36'	[-5.75/-2.57°C 751mb 39mb/208°] ZDC - liquid drops + needles + columns. P10 - needles + columns (500µm) CIP (cross) - needles 500µm
19.13.53	R14	FL80	76	50°54'/2°12'	CPI Capped Columns [-4.64/-3.07°C 752mb] - more ice here than before Rimed - frozen drops - CPI
[CN] 19.21.36	R14	FL80			Over Chulbitten [-5.63°C/-503° 752mb] Turb probe still rec'd despite warmer T. Chulbitten - reports fall streaks 40km was 4-6000H still patch.....

01
7
5
3

0
4
5.

16:15 - 18:30 = 35 mins/cycle

0500 H

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Flight No B.....424 Date21/01/09 NameK.N Bower Page9 of10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
[C1] 19.26.31	R14end / P5	FL60	243	51°6'/1°24'	Over Cloud [-5.7°C/-4.89, 752mb] good mix - small drops - large N° large ice (CPI) (some + columns)
19.29.09	P15E / R15	FL60	248	51°0'/1°30'	[-3.07/-2.55°, 810mb] Over Cloud :- Water drops - range sizes 200 / PIP (250 μm) (0.04 cm^{-3}) PIP 200 μm - narrow mode. CPI - drops - sticking together - 2DS 200 μm (100 & 300 μm) FSSP: 2 cm^{-3} mode 15-20 μm + bottom channel mode !! ODP: ones not high enough - can't see
19.38.00	sh				* lost total water Neuzer - again !!
19.40.51	R15end / P16	FL60	248	50°54'/2°30'	E 1.29°C / 0.5°C, 811mb
19.42.51	P16end / R16	FL40	242	50°54'/2°42'	E 0.65 / 0.1°C, 833mb methylenic
					(CPI) - occasional large blobby things - turbulence here
19.47.26	R16	FL40	84	50°54'/2°18'	[+0.79°/1.54°C, 874mb]
19.48.45	R16	FL40	82	50°54'/2°12'	Turbulence [+0.07°C/+1.1°C, 874mb]
19.51.55	R16	FL40	84	51°0'/1°54'	More turbulence [-0.67°C/0.89, 874mb]
19.52.36	R16	FL40	83	51°0'/1°48'	Seeing lot of ice now [-0.43/0.66, 874mb]
[C1] 19.56.51	R16	FL40	79	51°6'/1°24'	[874mb, -0.52°/0.1°C] Over Cloud bottom
19.57.34	R16end / P7	FL40	347	51°6'/1°24'	[873mb -0.46°/0.19°C] not allowed to PEPIS but climbing
19.58.40	P17end / R17	FL50	91	51°12'/1°18'	[842mb -2.15°/-1.26°C]
[C1] 20.01.33	R17SR	FL50	236	51°6'/1°24'	Over Cloud bottom [843mb, -1.57°/1.28°]

Arrived FL100 for transit

New plot, same times

Flight B424 15:11:20
Heading 242 deg Speed 264 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 52°12.0'N Long 0°48.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 225 deg
Temp -13.96C Dewpoint -26.52C
From 15:00:00 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54678 secs All SC
TECO NOx 0.15 ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B424 15:13:53
Heading 242 deg Speed 263 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 52°12.0'N Long 1°0.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/ 235 deg
Temp -14.65C Dewpoint -26.31C
From 15:00:00 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54831 secs All SC
NEPH BLUE SP 1.25 m-1
NEPH GREEN SP 1.42 m-1
NEPH RED SP 0.59 m-1

Transit FL100

Turn to start profile

Start P1

New plot, same times

Flight B424 15:24:35
Heading 172 deg Speed 244 knots Height 7.4kft Press 769mb
Lat 51°42.0'N Long 1°36.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/ 236 deg
Temp -8.12C Dewpoint -10.53C
From 15:00:00 to now

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	55473	secs
—	JW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0	g m-3
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0	g m-3
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0	g m-3

New plot, same times

Flight B424 15:25:37
Heading 172 deg Speed 238 knots Height 6.0kft Press 810mb
Lat 51°36.0'N Long 1°36.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/ 230 deg
Temp -5.88C Dewpoint -9.06C
From 15:00:00 to now

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	55536	secs
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	31.19	ppb

turn

P2 start from 5.4kft to 2.3kft

P2 end start R1

Just after Chilbolton (2s)

R1 2300ft just below CD

R1 Cloud and ppt filters off

Ppt again

R1 into cloud now

End R1

Start R2

Free of cloud base but ppt

Overhead Chilbolton end R2

Overhead Chilbolton - start P3

P3 - at diffuse CB

End P3 start R3 FL80

End R3, P4 start

End P4 start R4

R4 - bumpy here

R4 overhead Chilbolton

End R4, start P5 o/h Chilbolton

P5 end start R5 FL120

End R5 start P6 FL120

End P6 start R6 FL130 - now turn

Turb in turn – Snow (R6)

R6 Overhead Chilbolton

Overhead CH end R6 start P7

End P7 start R7

End R7 start P8

P8 end, start of R8 at FL150

Supercooled water in updraught

R8 – “CPI” supercooled H₂O

Temp PIP bimodal spectrum

R8 overhead Chilbolton

R8 end over CH start P9

P9 - Out through CT

P9 - Back in cloud

P9 - Through main CT

End P9 start R 9

R9 end P10 start

P10 CT

P10 int

P10 rec

Snowflakes – “CPI”

End P10 start R10

Icing detected on a/c sys

Overhead CH FL120 R10

Chilbolton - end R10 start P11

Liquid drops all m/ph + a/c antiIce

End R11 start P12

P12 end, start R12

R12 SLR starts

2DC snowflakes not doughnuts

R12 over Chilbolton

R12 over Chilbolton

End R12 start P13

End P13 start R13

End R13 start P14

End P14 start R14

Warmer and more ice

R14 over Chilbolton

End R14 start P15 FL80 over CH

End P15 start R15 at FL60

R15 FL60

Flight Summary B424

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
ASP	14:54:04	050	0.68kft	52.1N	0.6W						open
T/O	15:01:29	252	2.5kft	52.0N	0.7W						15:00:10
Video	15:05:51	049	6.8kft	52.2N	0.5W						started
note	15:15:52	242	10.0kft	52.1N	1.2W						water measures zeroed
PSAP	15:21:07	235	10.0kft	52.0N	1.7W						off
Profile 1	15:21:51	169	10.0kft	51.9N	1.8W	15:26:26	171	5.6kft	51.6N	1.6W	
QNH	15:29:49	171	5.5kft	51.4N	1.6W						995
qnh	15:30:20	171	5.5kft	51.4N	1.6W						1001 disregard prev
Profile 2	15:31:12	153	5.6kft	51.4N	1.5W	15:35:04	213	2.7kft	51.2N	1.4W	
Run 1	15:35:05	213	2.7kft	51.2N	1.4W	15:51:19	247	2.7kft	50.9N	2.8W	
note	15:35:43	236	2.6kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
psap	15:38:12	250	2.7kft	51.1N	1.7W						off
psap	15:39:50	247	2.7kft	51.1N	1.8W						on
psap	15:42:59	248	2.7kft	51.0N	2.1W						off
psap	15:45:28	248	2.7kft	51.0N	2.3W						on
psap	15:47:01	248	2.7kft	51.0N	2.4W						off
note	15:52:08	151	2.7kft	50.9N	2.8W						waters zeroed
Run 2	15:52:49	065	2.7kft	50.9N	2.8W	16:05:58	077	2.7kft	51.1N	1.4W	
psap	16:04:47	081	2.7kft	51.1N	1.6W						on
note	16:05:53	077	2.7kft	51.1N	1.5W						chilbolton
note	16:06:53	350	2.7kft	51.2N	1.4W						water zeroed
Profile 3	16:10:06	233	2.6kft	51.1N	1.4W	16:15:57	252	8.0kft	51.1N	1.9W	chilbolton
psap	16:10:53	247	3.2kft	51.1N	1.5W						off
Run 3	16:15:57	252	8.0kft	51.1N	1.9W	16:23:31	252	9.2kft	50.9N	2.6W	162215
Profile 4	16:23:32	252	9.2kft	50.9N	2.6W	16:25:16	251	11.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	162215

Profile 4	16:23:32	252	9.2kft	50.9N	2.6W	16:25:16	251	11.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	162215
Run 4	16:29:45	075	11.0kft	51.0N	2.5W	16:44:41	244	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	overhead chilbolton
note	16:38:42	073	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 5	16:44:41	244	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	16:45:55	258	12.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	overhead chilbolton
Run 5	16:45:55	258	12.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	16:57:54	255	12.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Profile 6	16:57:54	255	12.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	16:59:00	257	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 6	16:59:01	257	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	17:17:14	245	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	chilbolton overpass
note	17:11:20	072	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 7	17:17:14	245	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	17:18:19	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	chilbolton overpass
Run 7	17:18:19	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	17:29:53	259	14.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Profile 8	17:29:53	259	14.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	17:31:04	257	15.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Run 8	17:31:04	257	15.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
note	17:44:27	063	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 9	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Run 9	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
note	17:56:08	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.1W						water zeroed
Profile 10	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:02:42	259	16.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	interrupt
Profile 10	18:04:26	053	16.1kft	50.8N	2.7W	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	restart
Run 10	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	Chilbolton
note	18:15:38	073	12.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 11	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	18:22:06	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	Chilbolton
Run 11	18:22:07	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Profile 12	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 12	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:56:02	252	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
note	18:50:35	076	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
note	18:55:23	242	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 13	18:56:03	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 13	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	19:08:08	251	9.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
note	18:59:47	252	9.0kft	51.1N	1.8W						185930 - lights underneath

Run 6	16:59:01	257	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	17:17:14	245	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	chilbolton overpass
note	17:11:20	072	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 7	17:17:14	245	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	17:18:19	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	chilbolton overpass
Run 7	17:18:19	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	17:29:53	259	14.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Profile 8	17:29:53	259	14.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	17:31:04	257	15.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Run 8	17:31:04	257	15.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
note	17:44:27	063	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 9	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Run 9	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
note	17:56:08	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.1W						water zeroed
Profile 10	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:02:42	259	16.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	interrupt
Profile 10	18:04:26	053	16.1kft	50.8N	2.7W	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	restart
Run 10	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	Chilbolton
note	18:15:38	073	12.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 11	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	18:22:06	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	Chilbolton
Run 11	18:22:07	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Profile 12	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 12	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:56:02	252	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
note	18:50:35	076	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
note	18:55:23	242	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 13	18:56:03	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 13	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	19:08:08	251	9.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
note	18:59:47	252	9.0kft	51.1N	1.8W						185930 - lights underneath
Profile 14	19:08:09	251	9.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	19:09:34	250	8.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Run 14	19:09:35	250	8.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	19:26:33	243	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	chilbolton
note	19:21:38	079	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 15	19:26:34	243	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	19:30:15	245	6.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	chilbolton
Run 15	19:30:15	245	6.0kft	51.1N	1.7W						

End R15 start P16

End P16 start R16

R16

Turbulence here

More turbulence

Seeing a lot of ice now

R16 over Chilbolton

End R16 start P17

End P17, start R17

Run 8	17:31:04	257	15.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
note	17:44:27	063	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 9	17:49:55	255	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Run 9	17:55:59	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
note	17:56:08	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.1W						water zeroed
Profile 10	17:58:24	263	22.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:02:42	259	16.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	interrupt
Profile 10	18:04:26	053	16.1kft	50.8N	2.7W	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	restart
Run 10	18:08:18	070	12.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	Chilbolton
note	18:15:38	073	12.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 11	18:20:48	249	12.1kft	51.1N	1.4W	18:22:06	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	Chilbolton
Run 11	18:22:07	255	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Profile 12	18:34:51	257	11.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 12	18:36:26	255	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:56:02	252	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
note	18:50:35	076	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
note	18:55:23	242	10.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 13	18:56:03	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 13	18:57:26	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	19:08:08	251	9.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
note	18:59:47	252	9.0kft	51.1N	1.8W						185930 - lights underneath
Profile 14	19:08:09	251	9.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	19:09:34	250	8.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Run 14	19:09:35	250	8.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	19:26:33	243	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	chilbolton
note	19:21:38	079	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 15	19:26:34	243	8.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	19:30:15	245	6.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	chilbolton
Run 15	19:30:15	245	6.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	19:40:51	248	6.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	run 15 start 192915
Profile 16	19:40:52	248	6.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	19:42:53	242	4.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	run 15 start 192915
Run 16	19:42:53	242	4.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	19:57:59	357	4.4kft	51.2N	1.4W	
note	19:56:52	079	4.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						Chill-Bdog
Profile 17	19:57:59	357	4.4kft	51.2N	1.4W	19:58:37	085	5.0kft	51.2N	1.4W	
Run 17	19:58:37	085	5.0kft	51.2N	1.4W						

Start R17 SLR – overhead CH

Flight B424 20:12:16
Heading 244 deg Speed 217 knots Height 5.0kft Press 842mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°12.0'W Wind 26 ms-1/ 206 deg
Temp -1.08C Dewpoint 0.0C
From 15:05:00 to now

Current values
STATIC PRESSURE 842.64 mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -1.09 deg C
DEW POINT 0.01 deg C

Flight B424 20:12:33
Heading 244 deg Speed 218 knots Height 5.0kft Press 842mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°12.0'W Wind 26 ms-1/ 208 deg
Temp -0.93C Dewpoint 0.13C
From 15:00:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -2.29 deg (+ve E)
GIN LATITUDE 50.98 deg (+ve N) Draw plane

B424 xChat Discussion log

Now talking on #APPCLOUDS

<Doug_> test from FAAM

<Foggy> cloud looks good on Chiily radar main band just arriving

<faam146> thanks. It seems the cloud base is 2 km and top 6 km.

* radchobs (~radar@193.63.181.9) has joined #APPCLOUDS

<radchobs> Chilbolton Observatory is online

<Foggy> I am Tom , who is radchobs

<radchobs> radchobs represents the Chilbolton radar operators

<radchobs> At the moment, Chris is operating

<Foggy> Thanks

<Foggy> I am logging off briefly to change computers should be back in 10 mins

* Foggy has quit ("Leaving")

<faam146> looking good up here, low level runs good, climbing to higher levels

<faam146> once we have worked FL110, what do you want us to do next?

<faam146> thats to chris

<radchobs> The radar doppler spectra is showing bimodality between 3400-3700 metres

<radchobs> This could be supercooled droplets growing into ice crystals

<radchobs> Suggest we investigate this range of heights?

<radchobs> We also see gravity waves, wavelength 1 km, throughout much of the cloud layer

<faam146> Thanks. Just told the manager

<faam146> out next level is about 12000 feet.

<faam146> which is in the middle of your range

* blyth (~blyth@217.28.34.132) has joined #APPCLOUDS

<faam146> Hi alan, this is zhiqiang

<blyth> Hi guys. I'm on a train. How's the flight?

<faam146> It goes well

<faam146> Hi Chris, we will go back this layer again

* TomC (Tom@puhk3nwwky.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk) has joined #APPCLOUDS

<TomC> Now back had a problem with VIRUS scanner blocking port

<radchobs> Are you in the layer now?

<faam146> Just flew a bimodality layer at about 12k feet, where supercooled drops may grow into crystals.

<blyth> What' s the temperature?

<radchobs> we're seeing enhanced spectral width from about 3500m down to the melting layer overhead now, possible riming from fast doppler velocities (1.5m/s)

<TomC> Conference call in 15 mins any thoughts from aircraft

<faam146> we are doing profile run now, will fly below that layer and see the microphysics

<faam146> Chris, what are the cloud type above the layer?

<radchobs> Cloud type above the layer is cirrus up to about 6 km.

<faam146> Tom, instruments well except CPI and turbulence instrument.

<faam146> Thanks, Chris.

<TomC> Presumably turbulence probe iced up CPI in Manchester so

<TomC> About to ring into conference call

<faam146> This is snow at 13k ft

<faam146> There is snow at 13k ft

<TomC> suggestion 11 an take-off tomorrow

<blyth> At -15C?

<faam146> We are going to do the mission until 8pm local.

<faam146> We can stay the mission until 8 pm.

<TomC> Conference call ended take off suggested 11.30 tomorrow, possible slippage OK

<TomC> That means mission tonight ends on landing at Exeter

<TomC> CPI now fixed

<radchobs> have you found any supercooled? radar is showing cloud top descending now 5km o/h. shear layer at 3000m.

<faam146> Thanks for suggestion of take-off time.

<TomC> Have you encountered supercooled water important to identify where this is

<faam146> We found supercooledwater

<radchobs> where have you found supercooled water?

<faam146> Supercooled water at -16C and 13 kft

<radchobs> we are also seeing high ZDR and spectral width signatures at 3.5-4 km

<faam146> supercooled height is 15kft not 13 kft

<radchobs> we see a weak signature there too. the signature at 3500m is stronger, why not try there?

<faam146> Thanks, told mission scientist.

<radchobs> very interesting layer between 2200m and the melting level, possible riming/graupel formation.
<TomC> Very important that messages from radchops are relayed to Mission Scientist
* blyth has quit ("Leaving")
* faam146 has quit (Ping timeout)
* faam146 (~MPDS@203.38.13.15) has joined #APPLOUDS
* faam146 has quit ("Leaving")
* faam146 (~MPDS@203.38.13.15) has joined #APPLOUDS
<faam146> just disconnected and this is a test
<radchobs> you seem to be connected ok now
<radchobs> what are your flying plans now?
<faam146> could you summarize the conditions below 12 kft and the features, what you would like us to do?
<radchobs> we are seeing enhanced spectral width in fall streaks from 2000m down to the melting layer. suggest runs in this range
<radchobs> some high ZDR values at 2000m also, out to 25 km west of Chilbolton
<faam146> Thanks, we are planning
<radchobs> ok, let us know what you decide
<faam146> a summary of last few runs:
<faam146> run10: 18:04-18:20 12 kft Chilbolton
<faam146> run11: 18:22-18:36 11 kft
<faam146> run12: 18:36--- 10 kft, 50.9N 2.8W
<radchobs> we are seeing fast falling ice particles between 2700 m and 3500 m, did you find any evidence for this?
<faam146> Yes.
<faam146> now descending to 9000 ft for a slr
<radchobs> we see a patch of high ZDR between 1700-2200 m, 15-40 km west of chilbolton
<faam146> just told mission scientist.
<faam146> run 13: 18:56-- 9 kft, 51.1N 1.6W
<radchobs> also, layer of high ZDR also at 4 km, between 5-20 km west of chilbolton.
<radchobs> i guess this is cloud top
<TomC> to avoid timeout, still here
<faam146> Just told M. Sci.
<faam146> run 13 ended at 19:08 at 50.9N 2.5W
<faam146> run 14 started 19:09 at 50.9N 2.6W, 8 kft
<faam146> paul here briefly. going to do 8kft, 7kft and 6kft i believe than land exeter
<radchobs> thanks paul
<faam146> new update, 8kft, 6kft then 4 and maybe back up to 6kft. JC and KB in discussion
<faam146> ETA Exeter 20.30, all going well
<faam146> are the shafts you saw still precipitating out?
<radchobs> these seem to have advected past us now- some interesting streaks (high zdr) at 4-6kft about 20-45km west of chilbolton
<Doug_> copied eta, no need to use satcom to confirm
<faam146> reported to M. Sci.
<radchobs> can we have an update on current position and plans please?
<faam146> currently seeing drops around 200um, 2DS reckons some might be sticking together
<faam146> sure, currently at 6kft heading SW. i believe we are doing 4kft(NE) next and then back to 5kft (SW)
<faam146> at 19:34, at 51.N, 2.6W, heading 200 deg
<radchobs> thanks
<TomC> Please let us know when you leave station to head to Exeter
<faam146> at 19:43, height 4 kft, heading NE, the run before the last one.
<faam146> at 19:58, Just over pass Chilbolton, the final leg, 5kft
<faam146> heading west.
<faam146> at 20:04, about 16 min on station.
<Doug_> copied
<TomC> Sounds like a really good case, signing off now
* TomC has quit ("Leaving")
<Doug_> Dave K will be at security gate with transport at approx 20:45, you'll probably not be off the a/c until at least 9
though
<radchobs> safe journey back, cheers chris & andrew at chilbolton
<faam146> doug, ams here, i may need more than 30 mins
<faam146> Thank you all.
<Doug_> AMS, no problem, Dave knows u will be an hour(ish)
<faam146> thanks.
* radchobs has quit ("Leaving")
<faam146> landing, goodbye.
* faam146 has quit ("Leaving")

Cloud Physics Flight Log B424

Date:21/1/09	Operator:PDR	DRS Time:+0	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	DAU3 Time:+0	AUX1 Time:+0	Aux2 Time:+0
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		N		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref:	N/A	EI#1 V:	2.0	EI#1V:	N/A	Laser V:	4.0	Ref V:	3.4			EI#1 V:	1.86
	Flow:	0.80	EI#32 V:	1.6									EI#64 V:	2.62
	T (°C)	6.14												
	P (hPa)	988												

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Max size	LWC	
15:00:40																	Heaters switched on
15:01:00	~015	250-10															Exited boundary layer
15:31:12	055	10															Start profile 2
15:31:58	050	17															
15:33:11	040	21															
15:34:23	030	16															
15:35:05	026	11															End profile 2 start run 1
15:37:00	026	25															
15:39:00	026	35		20				Wet snow	6	1	4		0.005				
15:44:00	026	21		8				Water drops	10	1	1		0.003				
15:47:00	026	16		1				Water drops	11	1	1		0.01				
15:49:00	026	27		20				Water drops	17								
15:51:19																	End run 1
15:52:50	026	35		6				Water drops	32				0.002				Start run 2
15:55:00	026	43		5				water	59				0.001				
15:57:00	026	20		1				water	60				0.001				
15:59:00	026	30		7				water	61				0.001				
16:02:00	026	20		21				Wet snow	64				0.002				
16:04:00	026	25		7				water	65				0.001				
16:06:00	026	20		2				Wet snow	65				0				End run 2

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Max size	LWC	
16:10:09	026	20		0					66					0			Start profile 3
16:11:20	035	25		65				Small ice,needle s/columns	68					0.02			
16:13:25	055	30		20				Needles/c olumns , agg	71					0.04			
16:14:30	065	15		20				Small ice, agg	72					0.005			
16:15:30	075	22		10				agg	72					0.005			
16:16:00	080																End profile 3
16:18:00	080	25		60				Agg, small ice	79					0.005			
16:20:00	080	15		60				Agg, small ice	84					0.01			
16:22:00	080	50		100				Agg, small ice	95					0.01			End run 3 start profile 4
16:26:20	109	2		15				snow						0.002			End profile 4 start run 4
16:29:00	109	20		100				Agg, snow	125					0.005			
16:32:00	110	5		30				Agg, snow	130					0.005			Occassional bimodal
16:35:00	110	7		44				agg	140					0.004			Distribution seen on pip
16:40:00	110	60		35				agg	146					0.01			Modes at 1mm & 100 um
16:43:00	110																
16:45:00	110	2		20				Agg, plates	151					0.005			End run 4
16:46:20	120	20		15				Plates, agg	152					0.005			Start run 5
16:49:00	120	0		12				Agg, plates	155					0.005			
16:51:00	120	15		5				Agg, plates	156					0.001			
16:55:30	120	5		50				agg	165					0.01			Possible bimodal dist
16:58:00	120	40		150				agg	177					0.025			End run 5
16:59:00	130	36		130				snow	191					0.01			Start run 6
17:01:00	130	270		130				Agg,snow	212					0.03			
17:03:00	130	4		20				Snow,agg, plates	218					0.002			
17:07:00	130	2		10				agg	221					0.002			

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Max size	LWC	
17:10:00	130	0		15				agg	226					0			
17:17:15	130	0		0					227					0			End run 6
17:18:20	140	0		10				agg	227					0.005			Start run 7
17:20:00	140	50		70				agg	233					0.015			
17:24:00	140	7		70				agg	243					0.005			
17:27:00	140	5		10				plates	247					0.005			
17:30:00	150	50		90				dendrites	258					0.025			End run 7
17:31:00	150	0		8				agg	260					0.001			Start run 8
17:34:00	150	10		40				agg	266					0.002			
17:40:00	150	20		150					277					0.05			
17:43:00	150	70		45				Agg	289					0.01			
17:45:00	150	50		16				Agg	294					0.001			
17:50:0	150	16		36				agg	309					0.04			End run 8 start profile 9
17:51:00	160	18		10					316					0.002			
17:52:00	170	6		80					317					0.015			
17:53:00	185	15		0					318					0			
17:54:05	200	3		0					325					0			
17:55:00	210	0		0					325					0			
17:56:00	220	0		0					325					0			End profile 9 start run 9 PIP Hotwire DAT recorded during run
17:58:30	220	3		0					325					0			End run 9 start profile 10
18:02:45	160	3		0					345					0			
18:05:25	150	2		1				agg	357					0			
18:06:50	135	25		100				Dendrites, snow	361					0.02			
18:08:20	120	20		50				Agg,small ice	367					0.005			End profile 10 start run 10
18:15:00	120	25		25				dendrites	378					0.001			
18:17:30	120	15		100				Agg, plates	388					0.01			
18:20:00	120	3		30				Dendrites, snow	398					0.01			End run 10 start profile 11
18:22:05	110	7		20				snow	402					0.001			
18:30:00	110	30		325				Water drops	418					0.05			100um supercooled water drops
18:33:00	110	170		900	100			water	439					0			

Flight:

B424

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B424

Date: 21/1/09

Issues

Instruments

Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	Inlet iced at various times
Nevzerov	TWC alarm light on switched off @ 19:37
Buck -	experimental operation ->appears ok
FWVS	Not working
Turbulence	iced 16:27 and got worse through the flight

Aircraft

SatcomC	ops normal
MPDS	xchat worked well
ISDN Emails	Not used
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

21/10/09

Date: *[Signature]*

Flight No: 8424

Pre-Flighter: AMW/RLP

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	✓	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin				
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
8	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	✓	GPS	Checked	
13	x	INU	Align	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	✓	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	x	FWWS	Set up	
18	x	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	✓	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	✓	GE	Balance checked	
23	x	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	✓	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	✓	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	x	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	x	CGPS	Set up	
28	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
External				
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	x	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	✓	All other covers	Removed	
40	✓	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42		Tools	Avalon informed	
Avalon Checks				
				Signed
43		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44		ICEX applied		
45	✓	Traps checked & dry		<i>AMW</i>

[Handwritten mark]

